

Synthesis of Sphondin

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Sphondin, a naturally occurring furanocoumarin, has now been synthesised. The essential intermediate, 7-allyloxy-6-methoxycoumarin, has been prepared in a number of ways. By Claisen migration it yields 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-6-methoxycoumarin which, when subjected to osmium tetroxide-periodate oxidation or to ozonolysis, furnishes the corresponding acetaldehyde; the latter has been cyclized by polyphosphoric acid to sphondin. It has also been prepared by the nuclear oxidation of angelicin followed by methylation.

Sphondin is a furanocoumarin, first isolated as a minor component from the roots of *Heracleum sphondylium* L¹. Later it was obtained from the roots of *Pimpinella saxifraga*², *Heracleum lanatum*³, *Heracleum panaces*⁴, and *Heracleum sibiricum*⁵. It melts at 189-91° and gives a characteristic blue fluorescence in ultraviolet light. Its constitution⁶ was based on the following considerations. It has the molecular formula C₁₇H₁₆O₄ and a methoxyl group. On treatment with alkaline hydrogen peroxide it yields furan-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (I). This indicates that it is a furanocoumarin and an isomer of bergapten (II). As only a small amount was available, detailed study of its degradations could not be carried out. But ozonolysis in chloroform yielded a product which was an *o*-hydroxy-aldehyde (III). It gave a green colour with ferric chloride and on treatment with alkaline hydrogen peroxide it gave rise to fraxetin (IV). The constitution of the 8-aldehyde was confirmed by synthesis, starting from scopoletin (V). Sphondin was therefore 6-methoxy-(7,8-2',3')-furanocoumarin (VI).

1. Späth and Simson, *Monatsh.*, 1936, 67, 344; Jastrzebski, *Acta Polon. Pharm.*, 1959, 16, 215.
2. Wessely and Naugebauer, *Monatsh.*, 1953, 84, 217; Svendsen, Johan Tanum Forlag, 1954, 144.
3. Fujita and Furuya, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1954, 74, 795; 1956, 76, 535.
4. Svendsen and Blyberg, *Pharm. Acta Helv.*, 1939, 34, 33.
5. *Idem.*, *Planta Med.*, 1959, 7, 113.
6. Späth and Schmid, *Ber.*, 1941, 74B, 595.

The synthesis of sphondin itself has not so far been carried out. This has now been done by employing the new method of furan-ring closure which has been developed in this laboratory⁷. The essential intermediate required for this purpose is 6-methoxy-7-allyloxy-coumarin (X). It has been prepared in a number of ways:

(1) Aesculetin⁸ (VII) could be partially allylated in the 7-position, using allyl bromide and aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate; the allyl ether could be then methylated.

(2) Umbelliferone allyl ether⁹ was subjected to nuclear oxidation with alkaline potassium persulphate and the 6-hydroxy compound to methylation.

(3) Scopoletin¹⁰ (V) was subjected to allylation.

The allyl ether was subjected to the Claisen migration giving rise to 6-methoxy-7-hydroxy-8-allylcoumarin (XI). Oxidation, using osmium tetroxide and potassium periodate, yielded an aldehyde which was cyclised by means of polyphosphoric acid. The yield in the above conversion of the allyl compound to furan was about 20%. If ozone is used instead of osmium tetroxide-periodate for the preparation of the aldehyde, the yield is raised to 45% and the conversion is much more smooth.

When compared with the natural sample, the synthetic product agreed in m.p. (mixed m.p. undepressed), in all colour reactions as described earlier for sphondin, UV and IR spectra [given below in Figs. 1, 1(a), and 2].

Another method of synthesis, which may have value as following a possible path of biogenesis, is based on the consideration that sphondin is related to angelicin in the same way as scopoletin to umbelliferone. A convenient method of preparing scopoletin is by the

7. Seshadri *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 4, 256; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19B, 76.

8. Amiard and Allais, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1947, 512.

9. Seshadri *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 13A, 43.

10. Aghoramurthy and Seshadri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 411.

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FIG. 1. IR spectra of sphondin (synthetic).

FIG. 1a. IR spectra of sphondin (natural).

FIG. 2. UV spectra of sphondin.

para nuclear oxidation of umbelliferone¹¹, followed by selective methylation. The oxidation yields better results if the 7-hydroxyl is protected, i.e., umbelliferone methyl and allyl ethers provide very good yields. This condition is also satisfied in the case of angelicin. Earlier Naik and Thakor¹² reported failure in their attempt to oxidise angelicin (XII) with alkaline persulphate. In our experiments, this oxidation has, however, afforded a good yield of 6-hydroxyangelicin (XIII) which when methylated provided sphondin. This reaction has also been carried out with psoralen and isopsoralen (angelicin) mixture, which is readily obtained from the seeds of *Psoralea corilifolia*¹³. This mixture is difficult to separate as far as isopsoralen (angelicin) is concerned. The oxidation of the mixture takes place satisfactorily, only angelicin being oxidised and psoralene being left to be removed.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy coumarin (IX)

(a). To a solution of 6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (5 g.) in a mixture of acetone (100 ml) and 95% ethanol (10 ml) were added sodium bicarbonate (15 g.) and allyl bromide (2 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 12 hours. After filtering the sodium salts, the filtrate was concentrated and poured on crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate, dissolved in sodium carbonate (10%), and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave 6-hydroxy-7-allyloxy coumarin, which crystallised as colorless, thin rectangular plates from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (yield 2.5 g.), m.p. 145-46°. For analytical purposes it was purified by passing through neutral alumina column using ethyl acetate as solvent. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 5.1. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.0; H, 4.6%).

(b). 7-Allyloxy coumarin (5 g.) was dissolved in hot 10% aqueous solution of KOH (40 ml). The solution was cooled to 20° and potassium persulphate (6g. in 150 ml) was added dropwise during 2 hours with constant stirring. The deep brown solution was acidified with HCl to Congo red and the unchanged product was filtered. The clear aqueous solution was heated in a boiling water bath for 20 minutes with sodium sulphite (2 g.) and HCl (conc., 10 ml). The oxidised product was obtained by extracting the mixture with ethyl acetate. On recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum, 6-hydroxy-7-allyloxy coumarin separated as colorless plates (yield 2.0 g.), m.p. 145-46°, undepressed by admixture with a sample obtained by the 1st method.

11. Seshadri *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1951, 33A, 11.

12. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1696.

13. Rangaswami and Seshadri, *Ind. J. Pharm.*, 1943, 5, 105.

7-Allyloxy-6-methoxycoumarin (X)

(a). 6-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy coumarin (2 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (15 ml) and refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (0.8 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) for 4 hours. Acetone was distilled and water added to dissolve potassium salts. The undissolved methyl ether was filtered, dried, and crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum as colorless, long, prismatic needles (yield 2 g.), m.p. 110-11°. For an analytical sample the above methyl ether in ethyl acetate was passed through active alumina column. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 5.5. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 5.2%).

(b). Scopoletin (2 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (150 ml) and refluxed with allyl bromide (0.8 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) for 4 hours. Acetone was distilled and water added. The undissolved allyl ether was crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (yield 2.0 g.), m.p. 110-11°, undepressed by admixture with a sample obtained by the 1st method.

6-Methoxy-7-hydroxy-8-allylcoumarin (XI)

The above 7-allyloxy compound (2 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 200° for 2 hours under reduced pressure. The compound melted and did not solidify again during the heating. On cooling, however, a brownish yellow solid was obtained. It contained a small amount of the unchanged product. The mass was extracted with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%) and filtered. The clear alkaline solution yielded the required 6-methoxy-7-hydroxy-8-allylcoumarin on acidification. It was filtered, dried, and crystallised from ethyl acetate, yielding yellow, long, rectangular plates and needles (yield 1.2 g.), m.p. 145-46°. For analytical purpose it was purified by passing through neutral alumina using ethyl acetate as solvent. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 5.5. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 5.2%).

Furan-(2,3'-7,8)-6-methoxycoumarin (Sphondin) (VI)

(a). The above 8-allylcoumarin (0.25 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (20 ml) and water (20 ml) added. The mixture was stirred with osmium tetroxide (0.04 g.) for half an hour. Potassium periodate (2 g.) was added to the stirred mixture in small amounts and the solution was shaken in a vibro shaker for 1½ hrs. The solution was then shaken for 3 hours more. Finally it was extracted with ethyl acetate, the ethyl acetate extract washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and evaporated to dryness. The residue was heated for 10 to 15 minutes with polyphosphoric acid (10 ml), the mixture was poured on ice, and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in dry benzene and passed through active alumina column. On concentration sphondin crystallised as needles, yield 0.05 g., m.p. 188-89°. (Found: C, 66.3; H, 3.8. $C_{12}H_8O_4$ requires C, 66.6; H, 3.8%). The mixed m.p. with the natural sample was undepressed. The UV and IR spectra of the two samples agreed closely. UV absorption in methanol: (a) synthetic sample: λ_{max} 249, 303, 341 (log ϵ 4.3, 3.8, 3.7); (b) natural sample: λ_{max} 248, 300, 341 (log ϵ 4.4, 3.8, 3.7).

(b). A stream of ozonised oxygen (2%, 50 ml/min.) was passed for 25 minutes through a cold solution (-5°) of 7-hydroxy-8-allylcoumarin (0.20 g.) in formic acid (30 ml). The

solution was hydrogenated in presence of 1% palladised charcoal (0.5 g.) till the rapid absorption of hydrogen ceased. The catalyst was then filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was cyclised by means of polyphosphoric acid. The furano compound, so obtained, crystallised from benzene as silky needles, yield 0.085 g., m.p. 180-80°, undepressed by admixture with a sample obtained above.

Furano-(2',3'-7,8)-6-hydroxycoumarin

(a). Angelicin (1 g.), 10% aqueous KOH solution (20 ml), and potassium persulphate (3 g. in 100 ml) were used and the oxidation was carried out as described in the case of umbelliferone allyl ether. The oxidation product (6-hydroxy-angelicin) crystallised from methanol (yield 0.35—0.40 g.), m.p. 220-24° (decomp.). (Found: C, 64.7; H, 3.1. $C_{11}H_6O_4$ requires C, 65.3; H, 3.0%). UV absorption in methanol: λ_{max} 251, 295, 341 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 433, 384, 380).

(b). The above experiment was repeated using psoralen-isopsoralen mixture (1g.), obtained from the seeds of *Psoralea corylifolia*, in hot 10% KOH solution (20 ml), cooled in ice water, and oxidised with potassium persulphate (2 g.). The oxidation product was obtained by extracting with ethyl acetate. The yield of 6-hydroxy-angelicin was 0.2 g. and it agreed fully with the sample obtained in method (a). The recovered mixture could again be used for oxidation. After the repetition, the recovered residue crystallised from methanol giving pure psoralen without appreciable loss.

Furano-(2',3'-7,8)-6-methoxycoumarin (Sphondin)

6-Hydroxy-angelicin (0.1 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (20 ml) and refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (1g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.1 ml) for 4 hours. Acetone was distilled and water added to dissolve potassium salts. The undissolved sphondin was filtered and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 189-91°, undepressed by admixture with a sample obtained above; yield 0.1 g.

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